

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF YOUTUBE VLOGGING ON PURCHASE OF ELECTRONIC GADGETS AMONG THE YOUTH

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Abstract:

Social media platforms have become one of the essential part of the consumers in sharing, searching, and commenting activities as they are engaged in online shopping. Video blog users, known as “Vloggers”, are also becoming influential figures who can influence consumers shopping related decisions. With the development of internet and social media, YouTube vlogging has been considered as an effective marketing tool to reach the potential customers by the marketers. YouTube content creators are used to communicate with the public using videos and podcasts. This paper focuses on exploring the YouTube vlogging factors and their influence on the purchase intention of electronic gadgets among the youth. Specifically, it studies the effect of information quality, source credibility, information usefulness, information adoption and familiarity on purchase intention of customers.

Keywords: Video Blog, You Tube Vlogging, Electronic Gadgets, YouTube Content Creators

Introduction

In the modern era, social media is gaining its importance day by day with the increasing number of users. Social media offers a wide range of tools for communication and marketing hence companies and brands are highly interested in using this platform for information sharing and thereby increasing demand for their products. Social media influencers especially You Tube content creators such as bloggers and vloggers are becoming leaders on social media who have a strong influence on the minds of consumers. You Tube content creators communicate with the public through their videos and podcasts. A video blog, shortened as a vlog is user generated content that combines consistent storytelling and audio visual contents and is posted on a video sharing platform. People choose YouTube as a platform to share and post their personal experience after using a product or service, and the content on vlogs may range from daily life to traveling to makeup routine. The advertising industry keeps on searching for efficient methods to gain the attention of customers and they find influencer marketing the best tool for meeting their purpose. It identifies the individual that have influence over potential buyers and develops marketing activities around these influencers.

Statement of the problem

YouTube marketing is the practice of promoting businesses and products on YouTube platform. In this highly competitive world, brands find variety of ways to reach their customers. One of the recent and popular method adopted by brands is YouTube vlogging. YouTube vlogging and brand collaborations have gained attention to a large extend during this pandemic situation. Brands collaborate with YouTube influencers, and the subscribers have welcomed the reviews and suggestions of these YouTube. The increasing influence of YouTube vloggers on consumers purchase behavior and the importance of the vlogging subscriber's relationship are under researched. Most of the studies were concentrated on the influence of YouTube vlogging on beauty and textile products. A very few studies have been developed for studying the relationship between YouTube vlogging and purchase behavior towards electronic gadgets. Therefore, this study is an attempt to find out the effect of YouTube vlogging on purchase intention of electronic gadgets among the youth. The study mainly focuses on addressing the following research questions

1. What are the YouTube vlogging factors that affect the purchase intention among youth?
2. How does the you tube vlogging factors affects the customers purchase intention.

Significance of the study

Social media platforms have become an important part of consumers sharing, searching, and

commenting activities as they engage in online shopping. Video blog users, known as vloggers are becoming influential figures who can influence consumers shopping decisions. It is important to understand the role of vloggers who wish to develop a relationship between consumers via social media as a marketer. The vloggers play an important role as a brand influencers from the perspective of consumer behavior is thus an important academic endeavor and is the aim of this paper. This study addresses vloggers as brand influencers and subscribers as customers.

Objectives of the study

The present study aims at the following objectives:

1. To explore the YouTube vlogging factors influencing purchase intention of electronic gadgets among the youth.
2. To study the relationship between YouTube vlogging factors and purchase intention among youth.

Review of Literature

Anish Padhi (2021) The study titled The Impact of Youtube Influencers on Consumer Buying Behavior of The Gadgets, combined Youtube videos and their effects to study its effect on purchase intention of customers, new factors in Youtube are also considered in this study. The study found that marketers integrate their brands with high profile youtubers and this generates revenue for both companies and youtubers. **Ramya k. Prasad (2018)** The study Youtube Videos As An Effective Medium in Branding – A Study Among Urban Women In Mysuru City aimed to study the role of YouTube as a social media platform and its impact on creating visibility for brands and to determine the effect of opinions of YouTubers on its viewers. **Wilma Viertola (2018)** The topic of this study is the influence of YouTube marketing on a young targeted group which belongs to the consumer segment of generation Z. The research questions of how much the young audience is being influenced by the YouTube marketing regarding their buying decisions and how brands can use the results of this thesis. **Ponte, Maria (2017)** The study named How consumers perceive vloggers? Exploring Consumer's Perceptions And Purchase Intention Applied To Beauty Industry focuses on the social network Youtube and vloggers, applied in Portugal and Spain. The study was conducted to understand the influence of online reviews by vloggers on the purchase intention of customers. The study concluded that consumers find the reviews comfortable and convenient and influence their purchase intention.

Research Methodology

This study was conducted in order to assess the effect of YouTube vlogging factors on purchase intension of electronic gadgets among youth. To test the research model empirically a convenient sampling technique is applied. The instrument used is Questionnaire. The Questionnaire has two sections: Demographical Profile and five factors influencing purchase intention of the customer. A five point Likert scale was used. The respondents of the study were customers who prefer to watch YouTube vlogs before purchasing electronic gadgets. The sample size of the study is 121 customers.

Results and Discussion

1.1 Demographic Profile of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	64	52.9
Female	57	47.1
Total	121	100.0

Table 1.1 presents the Gender- wise composition of respondents. Out of total 121 respondents, 52.9 per cent are distributed by male and another 47.1 per cent by female. It is evident that male respondents are more.

1.2 Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	38	31.4
Employee	59	48.8
Business	11	9.1
Profession	12	9.9
Others	1	.8
Total	121	100.0

Table 1.2 presents occupation-wise composition of respondents. Out of 121 respondents, 31.4 percent were students, 48.8 percent were employees, 9.1 percent were doing business, 9.9 percent were professionals and 0.8 percent were engaged in other activities.

Hypothesised model

Source: Compiled by the Researcher based on extensive review

A Reliability Test was carried out using Cronbach’s Alpha, which measures the internal consistency of research constructs and the result is exhibited in the below table. The Alpha values for all the six factors are above 0.70, the threshold suggested by Nunnally (1978). Thus, it can be concluded that the scale has internal consistency and reliability. In other words, the items that are used in it measures what are intended to measure.

Cronbach’s Co-efficient Alpha- IQ, SC, IU, IA, F, PI

SL.NO	Factors (Constructs)	Acronym	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
1	Information Quality	IQ	4	0.890

2	Source Credibility	SC	6	0.88
3	Information Usefulness	IU	4	0.863
4	Information Adoption	IA	2	0.853
5	Familiarity	F	4	0.837
6	Purchase Intention	PI	4	0.832

Correlation analysis is carried out before conducting regression analysis in order to quantify the strength of relationship between the variables.

Correlation between Independent and Dependent Variable

Variable	IQ	SOC	IU	IA	F	PI
IQ	1					
SOC	0.697**	1				
IU	0.540**	0.561**	1			
IA	0.471**	0.561**	0.608**	1		
F	0.309**	0.553**	0.288**	0.316**	1	
PI	0.512**	0.557**	0.585**	0.509**	0.514**	1

Source: Compiled by the researcher

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

- The correlation between various variables are as follows:
- The correlation between Information Quality and Source Credibility is 69.7 percent.
- The correlation between Information Quality and Information Usefulness is 54 percent.
- The correlation between Information quality and Information Adoption is 47.1 percent.
- The correlation between Information Quality and familiarity is 30.9 percent.
- The correlation between Information Quality and Purchase Intention is 51.2 percent.
- The correlation between Source Credibility and Information Usefulness is 56.1 percent.
- The correlation between Source Credibility and Information Adoption is 52.6 percent.
- The correlation between Source Credibility and Familiarity is 55.3 percent.
- The correlation between Source Credibility and Purchase Intention is 55.7 percent.
- The correlation between Information Usefulness and Information adoption is 60.8 percent.
- The correlation between Information Usefulness and Familiarity is 28.8 percent.
- The correlation between Information Usefulness and Purchase Intention is 58.5 percent.
- The correlation between Information Adoption and Familiarity is 31.6 percent.
- The correlation between Information Adoption and Purchase Intention is 50.9 percent.
- The correlation between Familiarity and Purchase Intention is 51.4 percent.

Regression Analysis was conducted to measure the influence of IQ, SOC, IU, IA and F on PI. The independent variables are IQ, SOC, IU, I, F and dependent variable is PI.

Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Standard error of the estimate	Durbin Watson
1	0.714a	0.510	0.489	0.44282	1.935

ANOVA of regression Model

Model	Sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	sig
Regression	23.488	5	4.698	23.956	.000*

Residual	22.550	115	0.196		
Total	46.038	120			

ANOVA table showing the regression model fit presented in table shows that the model is statistically significant at 1 percent significance level (F=23.956)

Coefficients of Regression Analysis

Factors(constructs)	Item Acronym	Standardized Beta Coefficient	Sig. (P value)
Information Quality	IQ	0.171	.022**
Source Credibility	SOC	0.019	.023**
Information Usefulness	IU	0.313	.001**
Information Adoption	IA	0.127	.041**
Familiarity	F	0.320	.000**

*significant at 5% level

**significant at 1% level

Above Table presents the Standardized Beta coefficient values and the significant values of independent variables Information Quality (IQ), Source Credibility (SOC), Information Usefulness (IU), Information Adoption (IA) and Familiarity (F). The Independent Variables Information Quality (IQ), Source Credibility (SOC), Information Usefulness (IU), Information Adoption (IA) and Familiarity (F) has impact on the dependent variable Purchase intention (PI). Hence H01,H02, H03, H04 and H05 are rejected.

The data was analyzed in three different stages. The first section displays the profile analysis which includes a brief analysis of the Demographic profile of the respondents. In the second section the reliability of the measures were tested and found satisfactory. The multiple regression analysis of the measures was done in the third section and hypothesis formed at the outset were tested. It was found that Information Quality, Source Credibility, Information Usefulness, Information Adoption and Familiarity boosts customers to purchase the product after watching a YouTube vlog. Familiarity has the highest influence on Purchase Intention.

Conclusion

For advertising revenue, YouTube is becoming the “worldwide video platform” for competing world wide. With the growth of YouTube, marketers are rapidly connecting with the platform. The present study attempts to unearth the answers to the research questions of exploring YouTube vlogging factors and their effect on purchase intention of electronic gadgets among youth. It was found that Purchase Intention is dependent on Information Quality, Source Credibility, Information Usefulness, Information Adoption and Familiarity. Hence, companies and marketers could approach YouTube vlogging as an efficient marketing tool to promote their products to larger audience and can integrate with credible YouTubers. Customers could also review their perception regarding the Vlogs and overview how vlogs affects their purchase behavior.

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